

**doing it
together
science**

**A collection of Citizen
Science guidelines and
publications**

We have collected guidelines and scientific publications on citizen science and DIY science in order to start a library of good practice that we hope will be useful for CS practitioners, researchers seeking to establish CS projects and decision makers. This work is being conducted as part of the “Doing It Together Science” ([DITOs](#)) project to strengthen the knowledge base in CS and DIY science and support policy engagement for RRI.

The collection pays particular attention to six components of [Responsible Research and Innovation \(RRI\)](#) - Governance, Science Education, Ethics, Open Access, Gender and Public Engagement. RRI is a cross-cutting issue in Horizon2020, the EU’s Programme for Research and Innovation, that aims to construct societies in which research and innovation practices work towards sustainable, ethically adequate, and socially acceptable outcomes (find out more [here](#)). RRI also seeks to make discussions related to research more open to the public and to involve society in discussions on how science and technology can contribute to desirable futures ([RRI Tools: towards RRI in action](#)). We refer to these [six](#) components of RRI in order to explore how they are relevant to and addressed by citizen science (see also this [blog post on “How responsible is Citizen Science?”](#) and the [ECSA working group on CS and RRI](#)). For this reason, the RRI components have been adopted as key criteria to sort the review presented in this collection.

The two tables presented below include guidelines freely available online and scientific publications (open source and not). If you are interested in exploring a particular RRI component further, please use the legend to identify which documents addresses the component of interest for you.

Such a collection can only be work in progress – so please contact us via ditos@mfn-berlin.de to include any other important guidelines or papers.

There is also a [Zotero database on citizen science literature](#) established by [CSA](#).

Legend of RRI Key areas covered:

E - [Ethics](#)

GE - [Gender Equality](#)

GO - [Governance](#)

OA - [Open Access](#)

PE - [Public Engagement](#)

SE - [Science Education](#)

Selection of Guidelines that cover RRI Key Areas

RRI Key Areas Covered						Title	Author	Year	Language
E		G O		P E	S E	Green Paper Citizen Science Strategy 2020 for Germany	GEWISS	2016	English, German
				P E	S E	CS für alle - Eine Handreichung für CS - Beteiligte	GEWISS	2016	German
				P		Storytelling für CS: Tipps zur	GEWISS	2016	German

				E		erfolgreichen Konzeption und Durchführung eines Storytelling- Workshops			
E		G O		P E	S E	White Paper on Citizen Science for Europe	Fermín Serrano Sanz, Teresa Holoher-Ertl, Barbara Kieslinger, Francisco Sanz García and Cândida G. Silva	2014	English
				P E	S E	User's Guide for Evaluating Learning	Cornell Lab of Ornithology	2014	English

[Outcomes in CS](#)

P
E

[Introduction to the User's Guide for Evaluating Learning Outcomes from CS](#)

Cornell Lab of Ornithology

2015

English

P
E

[CS Framework Review: Informing a Framework for CS within the US Fish and Wildlife Service](#)

Cornell Lab of Ornithology

2015

English

		G O		P E		Proceedings of the CS Toolkit Conference - June 20 - 23, 2007	Cornell Lab of Ornithology	2007	English
E				P E		Best Practices for Managing Intellectual Property in CS	Commons Lab	2015	English
E						Typology of CS Projects from an Intellectual Property Perspective	Commons Lab	2015	English

		G O				CS and Policy: A European Perspective	Commons Lab	2015	English
E		G O				Managing Intellectual Property Rights in CS – A Guide for Researchers and Citizen Scientists	Commons Lab	2015	English
E	G E	G O		P E	S E	RRI Tools: Project briefing sheet	RRI Tools	2016	English

		G O			S E	Report on the analysis of needs and constraints of the stakeholder groups in RRI practices in Europe	RRI Tools	2015	English
E	G E	G O		P E	S E	A catalogue of good RRI practices	RRI Tools	2015	English
				P E	S E	Australian Guide to Running a BioBlitz	Australian Citizen Science Association	2015	English

				P E	S E	Guide to CS	Natural History Museum and NERC Centre for Ecology & Hydrology for UK	2012	English
E						Kriterienkatalog zur Bewertung von CS Projekten und Projektanträgen	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation	2015	German
		G O		P E		Data Management Guide for Public Participation in Scientific Research	DataONE Public Participation in Scientific Research Working Group	2013	English

G
O

P
E

[Science for
Environment
Policy In-depth
Report:
Environmental
CS](#)

Science
Communication
Unit, University
of the West of
England (UWE),
Bristol

2013

English

P
E

S
E

[Guide to
Running a
BioBlitz 2.0](#)

Nhm, Bristol
Natural History
Consortium,
Stockholm
Environment
Institute,
Marine
Biological
Association of
the UK

2013

English

P

[A Regional
Approach to the](#)

Scott R. Loarie
and James P.

2011

English

				E		Global Amphibian BioBlitz	Lewis		
				P E		Community Planning Toolkit - Community Engagement	Community Places	2014	English
				P E		Engaging Queenslanders: A guide to community engagement methods and techniques	Queensland Government Department of Communities	2007	English

P
E

[Putting Strategies into Practice: Engaging and Learning for Conservation Workshop on Public Participation in Scientific Research](#)

Center for Biodiversity and Conservation
American Museum of Natural History,
Cornell Lab of Ornithology,
National Audubon Society

2011

English

P
E

[Public Participation in Scientific Research: Defining the Field and Assessing Its Potential for Informal Science Education](#)

Center for Advancement of Informal Science Education

2009

English

P
E

S
E

[DIY
Development
Impact & You,
Practical Tools
to Trigger &
Support Social
Innovation](#)

Theo Keane,
Brenton Caffin,
Michael Soto,
Ayush Chauhan,
Rikta
Krishnaswamy,
Geke van Dijk,
Megha
Wadhawan

English

P
E

S
E

[Designing
Education
Projects, a
Comprehensive
Approach to
Needs
Assessment,
Project Planning
and
Implementation,
and Evaluation](#)

National
Oceanic and
Atmospheric
Administration,
U.S.
Department of
Commerce

2009

English

		G O		P E		Using Crowdsourcing In Government, Collaboration Across Boundaries Series	IBM Center for the Business of Government	2013	English
				P E		Collaboration & Team Science: A Field Guide	National Institutes of Health	2010	English
		G O		P E		CS and Crowdsourcing: Creative Approaches to Environmental Protection	US Environmental Protection Agency	2015	English

P
E

[Sustainable futures for Europe's Heritage in Cultural landscapes: Tools for understanding, managing, and protecting landscape functions and values](#)

Claudia Bieling,
Matej Batič,
Hélène Draux,
Brian Shaw

2014

English

[CS, Sustain – Journal of environmental and sustainability issues](#)

The Kentucky
Institute for the
Environment
and Sustainable
Development

2016

English

		G O		P E		From CS to DIY Science, An annotated account of an on-going trend	European Commission Joint Research Centre	2014	English
				P E	S E	Citizens, amateurs, volunteers: conceptual struggles in studies of CS	Patrícia Dias da Silva and Lorna Heaton	2015	English
E		G O		P E	S E	CS: New Ways for research, Policy Advice Paper	ETH Zürich	2016	English

P
E

[CS in den
Nationalen
Naturlandschaft
en, Anleitung
zur Entwicklung
von
Bürgerwissensch
afts-Projekte](#)

EUROPARC
Deutschland e.
V.

2016

German

G
O

[National
Advisory Council
for
Environmental
Policy and
Technology, EPA
Strategic
Directions on
Using Citizen
Science for
Environmental
Protection](#)

US
Environmental
Protection
Agency

English

		G O	O A	P E		Addressing Societal and Scientific Challenges through CS and Crowdsourcing	Science and Technology Policy, The White House, Washington	2015	English
		G O				Science for Environment Policy - Identifying emerging risks for environmental policies	Science Communication Unit, University of the West of England (UWE), Bristol	2016	English
				P E		Choosing and Using CS: a guide to when and how to use	Centre for Ecology & Hydrology	2014	English

						CS to monitor biodiversity and the environment			
				P e		Ist mein Projekt für CS geeignet? Ein Wegweiser für naturwissenschaftliche Fächer	Arbeitsgruppe für Citizen Science, Institut für Zoologie, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien	2014	German
			G O	P E		Voices for RRI: Engaging Citizens to Shape EU Research Policy on Urban Waste	Jacqueline E.W. Broerse, Lia van der Ham, Barbara M. Tielemans, Marzia	2014	English

							Mazzonetto		
				P E		A Roadmap for Citizen Researchers in the Age of Digital Culture	Antonella Fresa and Börje Justrell	2015	English
E						FUTURE BRIEF: Synthetic biology and biodiversity	Science Communication Unit, University of the West of England (UWE), Bristol	2015	English
			G	P	S	Synthetic genomics:	Garfinkel et al.	2007	English

			O	E	E	options for governance			
E				P E	S E	Myths and realities of Do-It-Yourself Biology	Grushkin et al.	2013	English
		G O		P E	S E	CS and Smart Cities	European Commission	2014	English
		G O	O A			Open Digital Science - Final study report	E. Prem, F.S.Sanz, M. Lindorfer, D. Lampert, J. Irran	2016	English

E	G E	G O	O A	P E	S E	Indicators for promoting and monitoring RRI - Report from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators For RRI	European Commission	2015	English
E				P E	S E	TAB report on 'Synthetic biology – The next phase of biotechnology and genetic engineering	Office of Technology Assessment at the German Bundestag	2015	English, German
E	G E	G O		P E	S E	Citizen science at universities: Trends, guidelines and	League of European Research Universities	2016	English

recommendations (LERU)

E GOPE UNESCO WSIS+10 Working Papers United Nations 2013 English

GO UNESCO WSIS+10 Outcome Documents International Telecommunication Union (ITU) 2014 English

GOPE Practices to Engage Citizens and Effectively Implement Federal United States Government Accountability Office 2016 English

						Initiatives			
E		G O		P E		Agency Liability Stemming from Citizen- Generated Data	Commons Lab	2014	English
E		G O		P E		Annual operating plan 2013-2014	Scottish Environmental Protection Agency	2013	English
E		G O	O A			Changing What Counts: How Can Citizen- Generated and Civil Society	Jonathan Gray	2016	English

[Blank orange box] [Data Be Used as an Advocacy Tool to Change Official Data Collection?](#) [Blank orange box] [Blank orange box] [Blank orange box]

[Blank white box] [Blank white box] G O [Blank white box] P E [Blank white box] [Citizen Science and Environmental Monitoring: Towards a Methodology for Evaluating Opportunities, Costs and Benefits](#) [Blank white box] UK Environmental Observation Framework [Blank white box] 2016 [Blank white box] English

E [Blank orange box] G O [Blank orange box] P E [Blank orange box] [Clearing The Path: Citizen Science and](#) [Blank orange box] Commons Lab [Blank orange box] 2016 [Blank orange box] English

[Public Decision Making in the United States](#)

G
O

P
E

[Crowdsourcing, Citizen Science, and the Law: Legal Issues Affecting Federal Agencies](#)

Commons Lab

2015

English

E

G
O

P
E

[From Citizen Science to Do It Yourself Science: An annotated account of an on-going movement](#)

European Commission

2014

English

		G O		P E	S E	Environmental Citizen Science	The Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology	2014	English
		G O		P E		Participatory Sensing A citizen-powered approach to illuminating the patterns that shape our world	UCLA's Center for Embedded Networked Sensing (CENS)	2011	English
				P E	S E	Citizen science at universities: Trends, guidelines and recommendatio	League of European Research Universities (LERU)	2016	English

						ns			
			O A	P E		Open innovation, open science, open to the world - a vision for Europe	European Commission	2016	English
		G O		P E	S E	Understanding Motivations for Citizen Science	UK Environmental Observation Framework	2016	English
E		G O		P E		Science for environmental	European Commission	2016	English

						sustainability			
		G O		P E		Making the most of our evidence: A strategy for Defra and its network	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	2014	English
		G O		P E		Citizen Science and Smart Cities	European Commission	2014	English
		G O		P E		State-of-the Art Study in Citizen Observatories: Technological Trends,	Finnish Environment Institute	2016	English

						Development Challenges and Research Avenues			
E				P E		The Principles of Planning, Collecting and Using Citizen Science Data	UK-Environmental Observation Framework (UK-EOF)	2016	English
				P E		Volunteers for Weather, Climate and Water	World Meteorological Organization	2001	English

		G O		P E	S E	NACEPT 2016 Report: Environmental Protection Belongs to the Public, A Vision for Citizen Science at EPA	National Advisory Council for Environmental Policy and Technology (NACEPT)	2016	English
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Selection of Scientific Papers and Books that cover RRI Key Areas

RRI Key Areas Covered						Title	Authors	Year	Language
				PE	SE	CS: A Developing Tool for Expanding Science	Rick Bonney, Caren B. Cooper, Janis Dickinson,	2009	English

[Knowledge and Scientific Literacy](#)

Steve Kelling,
Tina Phillips,
Kenneth V.
Rosenberg and
Jennifer Shirk

[Scientific Knowledge and Attitude Change: The Impact of a CS Project](#)

Dominique
Brossard,
Bruce
Lewenstein
and Rick
Bonney

[CS as an Ecological Research Tool: Challenges and Benefits](#)

Janis L.
Dickinson,
Benjamin
Zuckerberg
and David N.
Bonter

PE

SE

PE

SE

2012

English

2010

English

		GO		PE	SE	A review of CS and community-based environmental monitoring: issues and opportunities	Cathy C. Conrad and Krista G. Hilchey	2010	English
				PE	SE	Creating a Successful CS Model to Detect and Report Invasive Species	Travis Gallo and Damon Waitt	2011	English
				PE	SE	BioBlitzes help science communicators engage local communities in	Erin Roger and Sarah Klistorner	2016	English

[environmental
research](#)

GO

PE

SE

[CS: a new approach to
advance ecology,
education, and
conservation](#)

Hiromi Kobori,
Janis L.
Dickinson,
Izumi
Washitani, Ryo
Sakurai,
Tatsuya
Amano, Naoya
Komatsu,
Wataru
Kitamura,
Shinichi
Takagawa,
Kazuo
Koyama,
Takao
Ogawara and
A. J. Miller-
Rushing

2015

English

		GO		PE	SE	The future of CS	Michael Mueller, Deborah Tippins, and Lynn Bryan	2012	English
				PE	SE	A new dawn for CS	Jonathan Silvertown	2009	English
				PE	SE	Thinking Scientifically during Participation in a CS Project	Deborah J. Trumbull, Rick Bonney, Derek Bascom and Anna Cabral	2000	English
		GO		PE	SE	From Conservation to Crowdsourcing: A	Andrea Wiggins and	2011	English

						Typology of CS	Kevin Crowston		
		GO		PE		Constructing the scientific citizen: Science and democracy in the biosciences	Alan Irwin	2001	English
E		GO		PE	SE	CS: Can volunteers do real research?	Jeffrey P. Cohn	2008	English
				PE		CS as a Tool for Conservation in Residential Ecosystems	Caren B. Cooper, Janis Dickinson, Tina Phillips, and	2007	English

							Rick Bonney		
		GO		PE	SE	Next Steps for CS	Rick Bonney, Jennifer L. Shirk, Tina B. Phillips, Andrea Wiggins, Heidi L. Ballard, Abraham J. Miller-Rushing, and Julia K. Parrish	2014	English
				PE	SE	Galaxy Zoo: Exploring the Motivations of CS Volunteers	M. Jordan Raddick, Georgia Bracey, Pamela L. Gay, Chris J. Lintott,	2009	English

							Phil Murray, Kevin Schawinski, Alexander S. Szalay, and Jan Vandenberg		
		GO		PE	SE	Beyond scarcity: CS programmes as useful tools for conservation biogeography	Vincent Devictor, Robert J Whittaker and Coralie Beltrame	2010	English
				PE		The Neighborhood Nestwatch Program: Participant Outcomes of a CS Ecological Research Project	Celia Evans, Eleanor Abrams, Robert Reitsma, Karin Roux, Laura	2005	English

							Salmonsens and Peter P. Marra		
		GO		PE		Government 2.0: Making connections between citizens, data and government	Chun, Soon Ae, Stuart Shulman, Rodrigo Sandoval, and Eduard Hovy	2010	English
		GO				Suggesting frameworks of citizen-sourcing via Government 2.0	Taewoo Nam	2012	English

		GO		PE		From e-government to we-government: Defining a typology for citizen coproduction in the age of social media	Dennis Linders	2012	English
		GO		PE		Government innovation through social media	J. Ignacio Criado, Rodrigo Sandoval-Almazan and J. Ramon Gil-Garci	2013	English
		GO		PE		As Science Evolves, How Can Science Policy?	Benjamin Jones	2010	English

E				PE	SE	Faculty perspectives on community-based research: "I see this still as a journey"	Caitlin Kennedy, Amanda Vogel, Clara Goldberg-Freeman, Nancy Kass, and Mark Farfel	2009	English
		GO		PE	SE	Can CS enhance public understanding of science?	Bonney, R., Phillips, T.B., Ballard, H.L. and Enck, J.W	2015	English
				PE	SE	Studying CS through adaptive management and learning feedbacks as mechanisms for	Rebecca Jordan, Steven Gray, Amanda Sorensen, Greg Newman,	2016	English

						improving conservation	David Mellor, Greg Newman, Cindy Hmelo-Silver, Shannon LaDeau, Dawn Biehler and Alycia Crall		
		GO		PE	SE	Making marine and coastal CS matter	John A. Cigliano, Ryan Meyer, Heidi L. Ballard, Amy Freitag, Tina B. Phillips and Ann Wasser	2015	English
				PE	SE	Online CS projects: an exploration of motivation,	Vickie Curtis	2015	English

contribution and participation

E OA PE [Is CS an open science in the case of biodiversity observations?](#) Groom, Q., Weatherdon, L., & Geijzendorffer, I. R. 2016 English

E GO OA PE [Learn from DIY biologists](#) Todd Kuiken 2016 English

E GO PE [The DIY dilemma](#) Nature English

				PE	SE	European do-it-yourself (DIY) biology: Beyond the hope, hype and horror	Günter Seyfried, Lei Pei and Markus Schmidt	2014	English
		GO		PE	SE	Links and Distinctions Among Citizenship, Science, and CS	Caren B. Cooper	2012	English
				PE	SE	DIYbio: Making Things and Making Futures	Ana Delgado	2013	English
		GO		PE		Producing "Participation"? The Pleasures and Perils of	Christina Dunbar-Hester	2014	English

[Technical Engagement
in Radio Activism](#)

[Do-it-yourself
biology: Action
research within the
life sciences?](#)

[Analyzing the Role of
Citizen Science in
Modern Research](#)

Stefano
Golinelli and
Guido
Ruivenkamp

Luigi Ceccaroni
and Jaume
Piera

2015

2017

English

English

GO

PE

SE

GO

PE

SE